

Agroforestry Policies in Spain¹

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¹ This document is the product of a Working Group on Spanish Agroforestry Policy, with the support of the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) and the EU AgroforAdapt and DigitAF Projects. It will be updated as policies change. Meantime, we encourage you to join the [Comunidad de Sistemas Agroforestales Y Cultivos Mixtos](#). Separate versions of the SWOT-A are available in [English](#) and [Spanish](#)

Summary

This AgroForAdapt and EURAF Report updates a previous review of agroforestry related policies in the Spanish CAP Strategic Plan. It adds sections on environmental policies beyond the CAP, including the Carbon Removals Certification Framework, the LULUCF Regulation, the Nature Restoration Regulation, the Nature Credits Communication, the Spanish National Energy and Climate Plan and selected Regional Climate Adaptation Strategies. It also benefits from responses to a questionnaire sent to agroforestry stakeholders in October 2025 and results from a workshop for experts from governments, unions and NGOs held in November 2025. Twenty recommendations for action are given for consideration by MAPA, MITECO and the Autonomous Communities.

1 Introduction

Version 2 of Policy Briefing #44 updates version 1 ([24/4/25](#)) based on responses to a questionnaire completed during October 2025 by 127 stakeholders in the Spanish agroforestry sector ([6/11/25](#)), and discussions in the 4th Expert Advisory Group of the AgroForAdapt Project ([18/11/25](#)).

This Policy Briefing has a common format with others being produced by the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) for all EU Member States. It will inform recommendations to be made by EURAF to the Commission in June 2026 for consideration in the draft Regulations being developed to govern the post-2027 CAP. The Commission's draft regulations both mention agroforestry:

- the proposed “**CAP Regulation for 2028-2034**” [COM\(2025\)560](#) - which mentions agroforestry in Recital 12 (*The CAP objectives should be pursued through support for investments implemented by farmers and forest holders. Such investments may concern, inter alia, infrastructures related to the development, modernisation or adaptation to climate change of agriculture and forestry, **agro-forestry practices**, energy and water, installation of digital technologies in agriculture, precision farming, diversification of income sources in other activities such as agro-tourism and bioeconomy*)
- the proposed “**National and Regional Partnership (NRP) Regulation for 2028-34**”- [COM\(2025\)565](#), which repeats the following definition: “*agricultural area shall be defined in such a way as to comprise only land which is used for agricultural activities, including when it forms **agroforestry systems***”.

EURAF's recommendations for agroforestry policy at an EU level are summarised in the [February 2025 document](#) “**Agricultural Trees for Resilient Landscapes: a vision for European Agroforestry**”.

This report has the following sections: 1) introduction, 2) definitions of agroforestry, 3) estimates of agroforestry area, 4) legal requirements affecting agroforestry, 5) direct payment rules and SIGPAC, 6) rural development payments and policies, 7) CAP performance metrics, 8) stakeholder questionnaire responses, 9) other environmental and climate policies, 10) SWOT analysis, 11) recommendations

2. Definitions of agroforestry in Spain

The European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) currently defines agroforestry as “*land-use systems and practices where woody perennials are **intentionally** integrated with crops and/or animals on the same land parcel without the intent of establishing a permanent forest stand. These systems can include trees in various arrangements, such as single stems, rows, or groups, and can be used for silvoarable farming, silvopastoralism, or intercropped orchards*”. Each EU Member States gave their own interpretation of “agroforestry” in their CAP Strategic Plan 2023-27 (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #22](#))

The Spanish CAP Strategic Plan ([PEPAC](#)) defines agroforestry as: “*Land use systems that combine tree maintenance with agriculture on the same land*”. The PEPAC establishes a maximum density of 100 trees per

hectare for “farmland and permanent crops with scattered trees (other than fruit trees)”, but also indicates that the Autonomous Communities (CCAA) may modify this percentage “taking into account the local pedoclimatic and environmental conditions, the forest species, the specific traditional cultivation practices in the region, as well as the need to guarantee sustainable agricultural use of the land in a similar way to that of the plots of the same area that they don't have trees”. Furthermore, this limit does not apply to the number of small trees in new plantations.

Article 4(3) of the EU CAP Strategic Plan Regulation ([2021/2115](#)) confirmed that “agricultural area shall be determined [by Member States] in such a way as to comprise arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland, including when they form agroforestry systems on that area”. Unusually for an EU Member State, the Spanish CAP Strategic Plan confirms that, “agroforestry lands that fall within the national definition of forest **may receive support** provided that it can be proven that agricultural activity is carried out in that area, and there is no double financing with aid for the rural development programme for forests”.

Silvopastoral systems including trees and shrubs are included within the Spanish definition of “permanent pasture”, which the [Royal Decree 1048/2022](#) (implementation of PEPAC) describes as: “tierras utilizadas para la producción de hierbas y otros forrajes herbáceos naturales (espontáneos) o cultivados (sembrados), incluidos los pastizales permanentes y que no hayan sido incluidas en la rotación de cultivos de la explotación durante cinco años o más, ni hayan sido labradas, aradas y sembradas con un tipo de gramínea o forraje herbáceo diferente durante cinco años o más. **Pueden incluir otras especies arbustivas y arbóreas que pueden servir de pastos y otras especies tales como arbustos y árboles que producen alimentos para los animales, incluso si las hierbas u otros forrajes herbáceos no son predominantes o bien no están presentes en dichas tierras.**”²

Only Ireland and Greece have a similar definition of permanent pasture which includes shrubby species over the whole national territory “even if herbaceous species are not predominant” (EURAF [Policy Briefing #29](#) - (Bertomeu and Lawson 2023). The Spanish CAP Strategic Plan emphasises that the presence of woody plants or shrubs does not prohibit classifying an area as permanent pasture “as long as the shrubs do not constitute an obstacle to agricultural activities”.

There are 19 mentions of *dehesa* in the Spanish CAP Strategic Plan (PEPAC - MAPA 2023b), which indicates that traditional agrosilvopastoral systems of high ecological, economic and social value, like the *dehesa*, should be favoured in the calculation of PEPAC. *Dehesa* is mentioned as the most characteristic agroforestry system in Spain, with 2.5 million hectares. When the words “agroforestry systems” are used in the PEPAC they almost always refer to *dehesa* systems.

In the PEPAC, the eligibility of permanent pasture areas for basic payments (BISS) is not based on the number of trees, but on the presence of non-eligible unproductive items³, such as areas without vegetation, steep slopes or areas of impenetrable vegetation that prevent its full use. The “**Coefficiente de Subvencionabilidad de los Pastos**” (CSP) now incorporates a “species factor” (determined by each Autonomous Community), which allows grazable woody shrubs to be included in the eligibility calculation (MAPA 2023c). The CSP is a weighted average based on a 5 m pixel basis. The formula is:

$$CSP = \text{Factor Suelo} \times \text{Factor Pendiente} \times \text{Factor Vegetación} \times \text{Factor Incendio} \times 100$$

This national model is provided by the *Fondo Español de Garantía Agraria* (FEGA) to the Autonomous Communities (CCAA). Most CCAA, including Aragon, Castilla-La Mancha, and Extremadura, adopted this

²Land used for the production of herbs and other natural (spontaneous) or cultivated (sown) herbaceous forage, including permanent grassland, which has not been included in the crop rotation of the holding for five years or more, nor has been ploughed, harrowed or resown with a different type of grass or herbaceous forage for five years or more. They may include other shrub and tree species that can be used for grazing and other species such as shrubs and trees that produce food for animals, even if grasses or other herbaceous forage are not predominant or are not present on such land.

³ Described in Section 4.1.3.6 of the PEPAC.

national methodology. Others, such as Andalusia and Catalonia, which had historically used their own methods, have adapted the national principles to their regional specificities. The four discount factors are:

- **Factor Suelo (Soil Factor)** - which excludes areas without vegetation, such as bare soil, rock outcrops (afloramientos rocosos), sand, roads, buildings, and other unproductive elements. It uses Sentinel-2 images (from October 2018 to October 2020) to analyze the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) throughout the year and allows the identification of seasonal pastures that show vegetative activity at different points in the year, preventing them from being incorrectly classified as "bare soil" as might occur with a single-date image. The resulting raster layer classifies each pixel with a value of 0 (no vegetation), 25, 50, 75, or 100 (high vegetation).
- **Factor Pendiente (Slope Factor)** - uses high-resolution Modelos Digitales del Terreno (MDT or Digital Terrain Models) provided by the Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN). Discounts are applied in tiers; for example, a slope of 60% or less results in a 100% factor (no discount), while a slope greater than 100% (a 45-degree angle) results in a 0% factor (total exclusion). The slope discount as calculated by the system is final and cannot be contested by farmers.
- **Factor Incendio (Fire Factor)**. This is a temporary administrative factor. It assigns a PEPAC of 0 to pastures located in areas under a "periodo de acotamiento" (a mandatory post-fire restriction period), followed by a "periodo de bloqueo" where the original PEPAC value is restored.
- **Factor Vegetación (Vegetation Factor)**. This uses high resolution LIDAR flights (e.g., 1.5 points/m² in Andalusia) to create a 3D scan of the national territory, discriminating vegetation according to its height structure. The system assumes that vegetation of a certain height constitutes a physical barrier to livestock. Any vegetation detected between 40 cm and 100 cm is automatically classified as 'matorral' (shrubland) and is considered a "limited access to livestock" with a grazability factor of 0. However, a new "species factor" has been included to recognise that some shrubs are palatable. This is controlled by the CCAA and some, like Aragon, do not yet apply this "species correction". For example:
 - Andalusia calculates a "Factor Vegetación Ponderada" (FVP) (Weighted Vegetation Factor) of 100% in tree-dehesa pixels, 75% in scrub-dehesa pixels and 50% for matorral.
 - Extremadura grants 100% eligibility to all tree-dehesa pixels - implemented via "[Resolución de 27 de febrero de 2023](#), de la Dirección General de Política Agraria Comunitaria" which lists palatable and admissible species- both within and outside of dehesa zones - including some which are recognised as valuable for animal health.

REC 1: Use a less restrictive and more transparent approach to calculating the "Coeficiente de Subvencionabilidad de los Pastos (CSP). MAPA and Autonomous Regions (CCAA) should agree on a list of grazable shrubs and recognise that LIDAR gives a poor estimate of the accessibility to shrub vegetation - particularly for goats. The 2026 changes in NDVI calculation discriminate against grazing of shrubs, meaning that agroforestry farmers will have to undertake an appeal (*alegación*) process and provide backup with geolocated photos.

3. Areas of agroforestry in Spain

The extent of agroforestry in Spain, based on work in the AGFORWARD Project (den Herder et al. 2017), is approximately 5.6 million ha. Within this, it is estimated that dehesa systems, based on oak trees, cover around 3.6 million ha, distributed mainly in five autonomous communities (SECF 2017):

- Extremadura: ~1,250,000 ha (35% of the total)
- Andalucía: ~1,000,000 ha (27% of the total)
- Castilla-La Mancha: ~750,000 ha (21% of the total)

- Castilla y León: ~500,000 ha (13% of the total)
- Madrid: ~100,000 ha (3% of the total)

More recent work by den Herder et al. (2020) mapped the overlap of 2018 % tree cover density (Copernicus 2020), with Corine land uses (Feranec et al. 2016) for six categories of agricultural land⁴ which were thought to have significant potential for the establishment of agroforestry (Figure 1). This established a map of "tree deserts" for NUTS3 regions in Europe (MVARC 2023). Spain had an overall "tree-desert index" of 70.1%, which is 15th in the EU-27 and is exactly the average value (EURAF Policy Briefing #26).

Figure 1: Tree cover density in Spain on cropland/grassland, using 2018 data from Copernicus and Corine. Deep red pixels indicate hectares with tree canopy coverage below 0.05%.

The ten mainland provinces with the highest "tree desert index" were Valladolid (92.8%), Zaragoza (91.4%), Albacete (90.9%), Cuenca (89.4%), Segovia (89.3%), Palencia (88.8%), Soria (88.5%), Burgos (87.2%), Teruel (87.1%) and Zamora (84.8%).

Another estimate of the area of "agroforestry" in Spain is provided by the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) - i.e. the *Sistema de Información Geográfica de Parcelas Agrícolas (SIGPAC)*. This mapping system provides 30 land use categories for use by agricultural managers in their annual administrative returns to record the use of plots and subplots (MAPA 2023a). There is no specific category for "agroforestry" but there are two categories which correspond to silvopastoral systems: "pasture-with-trees" (PA) and "pastures-with-shrubs" (PR). Across Spain these add up to 8.5 Mha (Table 1), or 23.7% of the total utilised agricultural area. Recent changes have increased the eligibility of pastureland with trees or shrubs slightly (4.7%) compared to the previous CAP period.

⁴ 211 non-irrigated arable land, 212 Permanently irrigated land, 213 rice fields, 232 Pastures, 244 Agroforestry, 22 Permanent crops.

Table 1. Area of pasture land-use in SIGPAC (PA: Permanent pasture with trees; PR: Shrub pastures; PS: Grassland) in the previous period of the CAP (2015) and in the current one (2023) (Agrodigital 2023)

	Land Use	Number of Parcels	Total area (ha)	CAP 2015 Eligible Area (hectares percentage of total)		PEPAC 2023 Eligible Area (hectares percentage of total)	
				hectares	percentage	hectares	percentage
Active Parcels	PA	665.313	3.537.994	2.388.649	67,5%	2.485.879	70,3%
	PR	3.289.847	5.019.676	3.022.172	60,2%	3.179.297	63,3%
	PS	2.882.928	2.231.318	1.969.774	88,3%	2.018.215	90,5%
Total		6.838.088	10.788.988	7.380.595	68,4%	7.683.391	71,2%

Note: The [National SigPac Viewer](#) contains additional layers of information. One of these layers (only available in Andalusia, Castilla-La Mancha, Castilla y León, Extremadura and Comunidad de Madrid) is “**Montanera**”. These plots are validated by each Autonomous Community as producing products eligible to be marketed under the label "acorn fed", established in Royal Decree 4/2014 of January 10. This is the quality standard for Iberian pigmeat. Another layer, called “**Communal Dehesas**”, delimits the areas of communal property declared under the Royal Decree 1048/2022.

A recently added SIGPAC land use category is “**Landscape Features**” (“Elementos del paisaje” - EPP). This includes: trees in groups, trees in rows, isolated trees, hedges, copses and forest edges (MAPAMA 2023) (Table 2). These areas must be protected by farmers as part of CAP Conditionality Rules (i.e. "Buenas Condiciones Agrícolas y Ambientales" - BCAA no 8). These landscape elements are described in Section 4 of Annex II of the Real [Decree 1049/2022](#).

Table 2: Coding of landscape features to be used in SIGPAC (Junta de Extremadura 2023)

TIPO DE ELEMENTO DEL PAISAJE	CÓDIGO	POLÍGONOS/LÍNEAS/PUNTOS
Árboles (aislados)	AB	Puntos
Setos	ST	Líneas
Árboles (en hilera)	AB	Líneas
Lindes	LD	Líneas
Terrazas (terrazas de retención, bancales, ribazos...)	TR	Líneas
Muros de piedra	MU	Líneas
Árboles (en grupo)	AB	Polígonos
Charcas (charcas, lagunas, estanques y abrevaderos naturales)	CH	Polígonos
Islas o Enclaves (Islas o enclaves de vegetación natural o roca)	IS	Polígonos
Pequeñas construcciones de arquitectura tradicional	CO	Polígonos

The dimensions and conversion and weighting factors of landscape features are shown in the CAP Strategic Plan (Table 3) but the rules to be followed by farmers in declaring these are not clear, especially following the removal of the mandatory minimum areas for BCAA-8 in the 2024 CAP “Simplification Regulation”. Farmers are still required to maintain these features, but the procedure in Spain to update the data and to monitor protection is unclear (EURAF [Research Report #59](#))..

REC 2: Publish fuller information on the distribution and value of Landscape Features. The EU CAP Simplification regulation (2024/1468) removed the need for arable farmers to maintain threshold value for areas of landscape features and non-productive areas. Yet landscape features remain protected and farmers will receive a red flag from the Area Monitoring Service if they are removed. These features are a new component of SIGPAC and MAPA could explain better the current rules and statistics (e.g. Result Indicator 34⁵) and the value to farmers of maintaining current landscape features, and the subsidies available for creating and registering new ones.

4. Legal regulations affecting agroforestry in Spain

Regional government frameworks for dehesa exist for several Autonomous Communities.

In **Andalucía**, [Ley 7/2010](#) (*Ley de la dehesa*) defines the “*formación adehesada*” as a forest surface occupied by a tree layer with a canopy cover (“*fracción de cabida cubierta*” - FCC) between 5% and 75%. The 5% minimum prohibits landowners from clearing all trees, and the 75% maximum gives a legal basis to combat land abandonment. The subsequent [Decreto 172/2017](#) implements a 20-year strategic plan with mandatory revisions at least every 5 years, which aims to “*strengthen the resilience of dehesas against deterioration, aging, and climate change; demonstrate and promote integrated management; transfer the best available knowledge and technical innovations; and support the human capital that manages the dehesa*”. It is organised into 5 blocks: a) description of the dehesa, b) new uses and opportunities, c) analysis of current situation; d) action strategies, e) monitoring. A component of this is the *Plan de Gestión Integral* (PGI) which is a voluntary farm-level planning document for landowners, containing: a) an analysis and diagnosis of the entire dehesa holding, its natural resources, and its productive uses, and b) a detailed programming of all actions to be carried out during the plan's validity which integrates management of livestock, pasture trees, hunting and additional land uses. It provides regulations and technical manuals for the best type of pruning (*poda de formación, poda de mantenimiento and poda sanitaria*) and regeneration techniques.

In **Extremadura**, the initial legislation, Ley 1/1986 “*Sobre la Dehesa*”, has largely been superseded by technical forestry decrees. The most significant of these are [Decreto 118/2022](#) which proposes *Modelos de Gestión Forestal para terrenos adehesados* and Decreto [134/2019](#), which regulates the execution of forestry actions. Together these define specific “silvicultural guidelines” (*itinerario silvícola*) that landowners must follow, which are defined by the species, the state of the trees, and the farm's objective. The models are built on extremely long-term planning cycles, with a defined rotation (*turno*) of 270 years for Holm Oak (*Encina*) and 150 years for Cork Oak (*Alcornoque*). They also set a “regeneration urgency index” to classify the state of regeneration and mandate intervention in aging dehesas. Guidance is given on pruning and regeneration techniques such as “*recepes*” - coppicing or stump sprouting, with a maximum cut height of 10 cm above the ground, and “*apostados*” - thinning existing clumps of saplings to select the single best stem for future growth.

In **Castilla-y-León**, there is no specific “*Ley de Dehesa*”, and protection is managed as a patchwork of measures integrated into its general ley de montes ([Ley 3/2009](#)). The recent “[Disposición Adicional cuarta](#)” explicitly extends the law's articles on forestry exploitation to “*terrenos agrosilvopastorales*” and “*formaciones agroforestales*” and mandates that regeneration is obligatory if a forestry exploitation (like clearing or heavy pruning) results in a final stock of fewer than 30 living trees per hectare. The decree defines “satisfactory regeneration” as achieving at least 30 viable trees per hectare or a 20% canopy cover. The region also promotes protection through strategic, non-legislative initiatives, such as the “[Dehesa del Futuro](#)” project, developed in partnership with FAFCYLE (*Federation of Forest Owners of Castilla y León*) to improve sustainability and profitability.

⁵ In Spain the target for R.24 is 0.25% of UAA by 2027, but the latest Annual Performance Report shows a figure of 0% - since only areas which are paid to maintain landscape features are recorded in Spain - in contrast to other Member States.

In **Castilla la Mancha**, the primary legal protection is the general "*Ley de Montes*" ([Ley 3/2008](#)). The law provides the general framework for managing montes, including dehesas, but lacks the specific focus of the Andalusian or Extremaduran models. A "*plan estratégico para la recuperación y desarrollo de la dehesa ibérica mediterránea castellano-manchega*" [was proposed in 2008](#), but its current status is unknown.

Regional responses to threats. "*La seca*" is a devastating syndrome causing the progressive decline and death of *Quercus spp.* trees (Regenerate, n.d.) While it is a complex disease with multiple contributing factors (such as climate change-induced stress), its primary causal agent has been identified as the invasive oomycete (or water mold) *Phytophthora cinnamomi*. Its severity has encouraged regional responses, e.g.:

- In **Andalucía** a formal, state-led, "*Catálogo de Acciones Contra la 'Seca*" exists, managed by the *Instituto Andaluz de Investigación y Formación Agraria* (IFAPA). There is also aid provided to landowners for preventive phytosanitary measures, such as lime applications (*encalados*) (which may inhibit sporangium formation (Serrano et al. 2013) and the installation of sanitary fords (*vados sanitarios*) to disinfect vehicles and machinery, preventing the spread of the pathogen in soil (Junta de Andalucía 2018).
- In **Extremadura** the "*Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura*" (CICYTEX) has a strategy based on R&D for integrated control, including early detection techniques and testing alternative biological controls, including bio-fumigation, the sowing of antagonistic microorganisms, and the use of plants that produce inhibitory substances, and identifying and selecting "plus" trees (árboles "plus") which exhibit natural resistance to *Phytophthora*.⁶

REC 3: Create a "la seca" task force: The risk posed by "*la seca*" *Phytophthora cinnamomi* to oak dehesas in Spain is grave, and a national "Task Force" is needed to fund a coordinated, cross-regional action plan - focusing on control, mycorrhizal associations and breeding/selection for resistance - potentially using "new genomic techniques"

5. Agroforestry in direct payments (Pillar 1)

Pillar I of the Common Agricultural Policy (PAC) regulates farm income support through direct payments. It makes agriculture more profitable, ensures food security and helps farmers produce healthy and affordable food. Pillar I is funded entirely by the European Union. The two components related to agroforestry are Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) and Eco-Schemes.

5.1. Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) 8

The GAECs establish the land and livestock care requirements that must be met in agricultural management to receive direct aid. EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#) lists the GAEC-8 landscape features and non-productive areas chosen by all EU Member States in their CAP Strategic Plans. Spain opted to monitor the implementation of GAEC-8 by offering farmers the choice of all three options: a) at least 4% of the cropland of agricultural holdings dedicated to landscape features and non-productive elements (e.g. including fallow); b) that at least 3% of the cropland at the farm level is dedicated to non-productive areas and elements, when the farmer undertakes to allocate at least 7% of the cropland to landscape features non-productive elements, within the framework of an eco scheme; c) additional inclusion of N-fixing crops on up to 7% of cropland, providing that pesticide is not used. However, the 2024 "CAP Simplification" Regulation ([2024/1458](#)) removed this obligation, and part of the justification for GAEC-8.

Table 3 shows the landscape features selected by Spain, the conversion factors to areas and whether farmers are legally obliged to protect the features. One point of uncertainty is that the maximum permitted size of a "landscape-feature" copse is 0.3 ha, while the minimum size of a forest stand is 1 ha: implying that "large" copses (*bosquetes*) (0.3-1 ha) will not be legally protected. The Spanish national administration has

⁶ CICYTEX desarrolla un sistema de alerta que anticipa la propagación de la enfermedad de la seca en alcornocos y encinas <https://www.juntaex.es/w/cicytex-3?inheritRedirect=true>

also recognized the importance of GAEC-1 and GAEC-9 in supporting the conservation and sustainable management of *dehesas* (MAPS 2022).

Table 3 GAEC 8 Conversions, Weightings, and Protection Status for landscape-features selected by Spain (qv Royal Decree 1049/2022).

Type of surface and non-productive element	Conversion factor (m/tree to m2)	Weighting factor	Including	Protected
1 Buffer strips protection	6	1,5	Y	Y
2 Cairns	2	1	Y	Y
3 Cultural elements				
- Small buildings of traditional architecture	1	1	Y	Y
4 Trenches				
5 Field margins			Y	Y
6 Woody elements				
6.1 Hedges or tree-lined strip	5	2	Y	Y
6.2 Trees in a row	5	2	Y	Y
6.3 Tree groups	1	2	Y	Y
6.4 Isolated tree	20	1,5	Y	
6.5 Forest boundaries	6	1,5	Y	
7 Fallow lands				
7.1 Fallow land	1	1	Y	Y
7.2 Fallows for biodiversity, including honey plants	1	1,5	Y	Y
8 Others				
8.1 Islands of natural vegetation or rock and mounds	1	1	Y	
9 Ponds, lagoons, ponds and natural watering holes	1	1,5	Y	
10 Small wetlands				
11 Stone walls (m)	1	1	Y	
12 Streams				
13 Terraces (retention terraces, terraces and banks)	2	1	Y	Y

5.2. Ecoschemes

Ecoschemes are a new feature of the CAP 2023-27. They are annual payments which support environmental or climate actions additional to conditionality. Spain has defined nine eco-schemes, which apply to the whole country (Table 4), five of which are potentially relevant to agroforestry systems, and represent 60% of the allocated funding. Regional Authorities can make small adjustments to their rules, such as the period required to prove that the grassland is indeed being grazed.

Ecoschemes 1 and 2 are particularly relevant to silvopastoral systems. The description includes "*extensive grazing and the establishment of biodiversity islands or sustainable harvesting.*" Grassed Landscape elements (e.g. herbaceous strips) "*may not be mowed or harvested, but may be grazed.*" *Dehesas* are mentioned as typical of the wooded pastures which Eco-scheme 2 focuses on.

Three eco-regimes relate to "carbon farming: inert and herbaceous covers in permanent-crops" (6, 7, 8). These schemes aim to protect the soil between rows of permanent crops (fruit trees, nuts, olive trees), covering it with herbaceous covers or with inert material. Grazing of living vegetation cover is permitted, and this could qualify as a type of silvopastoral system. Harvesting of the crops is not permitted.

Table 4: Eco-regimes activated in Spain

ÁMBITOS	ECORREGÍMENES	N.º	TIPO DE SUPERFICIE	PRÁCTICAS
AGRICULTURA DE CARBONO Y AGROECOLOGÍA	PASTOREO EXTENSIVO, SIEGA Y BIODIVERSIDAD	1	PASTOS HÚMEDOS	P1. Pastoreo extensivo P2A Establecimiento de islas de biodiversidad
		2	PASTOS MEDITERRÁNEOS	P2B. Siega sostenible
	ROTACIONES Y SIEMBRA DIRECTA	3	TIERRAS DE CULTIVO SECANO	P3. Rotación de cultivos con especies mejorantes
		4	TIERRAS DE CULTIVO SECANO HÚMEDO	P4. Agricultura de conservación: siembra directa
		5	TIERRAS DE CULTIVO CULTIVO DE REGADÍO	
AGRICULTURA DE CARBONO	CUBIERTAS VEGETALES Y CUBIERTAS INERTES	6	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS TERRENOS DE ELEVADA PENDIENTE	P6. Cubiertas vegetales espontáneas o sembradas
		7	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS TERRENOS DE PENDIENTE MEDIA	P7. Cubiertas inertes de restos de poda
		8	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS TERRENOS LLANOS	
AGROECOLOGÍA	ESPACIOS DE BIODIVERSIDAD	9	TIERRAS DE CULTIVO Y CULTIVOS PERMANENTES (incluidos cultivos leñosos)	P5. Opciones generales P5. Opciones específicas de cultivos bajo agua

Ecoscheme 9 is also relevant to agroforestry since the areas listed include landscape features (stone walls, ponds, hedges, contour trees/shrubs and vegetated areas that act as shelter and habitat for insects, birds and pollinators, including edges and borders of cultivated plots. This eco-regime is related to GAEC 4 and 8.

The total uptake areas of these ecoschemes have been listed for each CCAA in the CAP Annual Monitoring Report for Spain ([Balance PAC 2024](#)), but it is difficult to measure the impact of ecoschemes without knowing the practices applied in SIGPAC parcels

REC 4 - Use SIGPAC to give parcel by parcel information on CAP intervention codes: MAPA should list which ecoscheme, agri-environment, and investment measure codes were implemented in which SIGPAC parcels, to allow the eventual impacts to be evaluated.

6. Agroforestry in rural development policies (CAP Pillar II)

Pillar II of the CAP helps rural areas of the Union to respond to economic, environmental and social challenges. It is more flexible than Pillar I, providing a “menu” of Articles defined at European level, which are applied in different ways at national or regional. . Pillar II is co-financed between the EU and regional or national funds.

There are 13 Agri-Environment-Climate (Table 5) and 15 Investment (Table 6) Measures in Pillar II. Of these, 13 could support agroforestry depending on the interpretation of the Autonomous Communities. Other Articles in the CAP Strategic Plan could be relevant to agroforestry, such as Article 77 (Cooperation) and Article 78 (Knowledge Exchange).

6.1 Agri-environmental and Climate Measures - AECM (Article 70)

Agri-environment and climate measures give annual payments to farmers for 5-7 years for measures beneficial to environment, climate and animal welfare. One measure in Spain is focused on maintaining newly-afforested and agroforested systems (6502.2), and six more which may be applicable to agroforestry (Table 5).

Table 5. Agro-environmental and Climate Measures of Pillar of the Strategic Plan of the Spanish CAP Article 70 (2023-28). In bold: measures related to agroforestry

Code	Measure
6501.1	Integrated agricultural production
6501.2	Sustainable crop management
6501.3	Commitments to promote and sustainably manage pastures
6501.4	Beekeeping for biodiversity
6501.5	Protection of birdlife
6501.6	Maintenance or improvement of habitats and traditional agricultural activities that preserve biodiversity
6501.7	Alternatives to pesticides and herbicides
6501.8	Practices for soil improvement and erosion control
6502.1	Forest management commitments
6502.2	Commitments to maintain forestry and agroforestry systems
6503	Agri-environmental management commitments in organic farming
6504	Commitments to animal welfare and health
6505	Commitments to conservation of genetic resources

- **AECM 6502.2 - Commitments to maintain tree plantations and agroforestry systems:** These grants support the conservation of plantations, facilitating their development so that they can provide ecosystem services (e.g., carbon capture and storage, hydrological regulation, cultural and recreational services, soil protection, and conservation of biodiversity), including habitats, and landscape maintenance. The actions will be verified through monitoring for periods of five to seven years, and the resulting loss of income and/or increased costs will be compensated by an annual premium per hectare, or a single payment in justified cases. The measure includes specific budgets for agroforestry systems in Cantabria (500 ha), Extremadura and Galicia (areas not indicated).
- **AECM 6501.1 - Integrated Production:** which aims to adopt changes in agricultural practices that contribute positively to the environment and climate, achieved through "integrated production standards", with actions that include: a) promotion and improvement of biodiversity; b) maintenance of soil vegetation cover; c) analysis of soil, irrigation water and foliage in perennial crops; d) establishing fertilisation programmes for crops; e) removal weeds and crop residues; f) ground preparation; g) irrigation techniques, and h) implementation of rotations.
- **AECM 6501.2 - Sustainable crop management:** which mentions the "preservation of landscape features", such as the margins, trees, banks and scattered trees.
- **AECM 6501.3 - Commitments to promote and sustainably manage pastures:** This measure envisages the following actions: a) extensive grazing with animals of certain species; b) practice of transhumance; c) annual grazing plans that include rotation, movement of animals and use of pastures outside the farm; d) traditional pasture management with seasonal movement of livestock with the same number of animals for at least five consecutive years; e) the temporary exclusion of grazing, consisting of leaving at least 20% of the contract area ungrazed each year for 3 months and on a rotational basis; f) extensification of grazing by respecting maximum livestock load limits; g) mowing, no tillage, controlled grazing, limitations in fertilisation, surface regeneration (avoiding invasive species or shrubby vegetation). An example of the this measure is that of Castilla y León, which envisages the planting of trees (at a minimum density of 10 trees/ha) on areas with less than 60 trees/ha, as well as the conversion of wire fences present in green hedges, by implementing woody margins in at least 25 linear m each year. In Catalonia it includes the maintenance of woody perimeters and preserving the shrub and/or tree vegetation.
- **AECM 6501.6 - Maintenance or improvement of habitats and traditional agricultural activities that preserve biodiversity:** including the maintenance and conservation of elements and functions of

traditional landscapes: natural vegetation, in sets, stone walls... In Castilla y León it includes minor crops, specifically plantations of holm-oak for truffle production and permanent crops in unique landscapes, where plots have linear features like hedges or stone walls with at least 100m length per hectare. In the Community of Madrid this measure promotes the maintenance of landscape features, such traditional hedges, walls or areas of natural vegetation..

- **AECM 6501.8 - Practices for soil improvement and fight against erosion:** which includes a) maintenance or implementation of vegetation cover, woody margins and islands of vegetation; b) conservation of landscape features that protect the soil from the effects of runoff, such as walls, cairns, terraces. In the Canary Islands, the conservation of isolated trees or bushes and islands of scrub and thorns is mentioned.
- **AECM 6502.1 - Forest management commitments:** aims to promote sustainable forest management by increasing the multifunctionality and resilience of forests, and improving the prevention of forest fires and their subsequent restoration. Forestry operations include interventions favourable to silvopastoralism, such as pruning, grubbing-up or brush-clearing. Some examples include modification to the use of grasses for fire prevention or habitat conservation. In Extremadura and other regions forest grazing is promoted to prevent fires and to conserve habitats and diversify and enhance the coverage of native forest species.

Other measures such as AECM 6501.5 (Protection of avifauna) could also promote agroforestry, although it is not specifically mentioned.

The Implementation of Agri-environment Climate measures is summarised in the “Balance-PAC” reports on the [MAPA website](#), for [2023](#) and [2024](#), but gives no information on Agrienvironmental Climate Payments. The impact of these measures will remain unclear unless an indication is provided of which AECM measures were implemented on which SIGPAC Parcel.

6.2 Investment Measures - INVEST (Articles 73)

Investment measures are single payments which cover the costs of productive or non-productive investments. One measure is focused on the establishment of forestry and agroforestry systems (6881.1), and at least 5 more that could potentially be used for agroforestry (Table 6).

- **INVEST 6881.1 - Non-productive forestry investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems.** The objective is to increase the forest area, conserve and restore agroforestry systems, improve the prevention of forest fires and their subsequent restoration, and support silvicultural treatments for the conservation of forests and their adaptation to climate change. Reforestation actions cover agricultural and forest lands with little tree cover. Agroforestry systems can be established by introducing trees into agricultural land or forest land with little tree cover, or by thinning forest vegetation to allow livestock or agricultural use, always in accordance with article 40 of Law 43/2003 on Forests. Funded actions include: a) establishment of forest trees, including replacement of mortality and/or protection of natural regeneration, b) treatment of existing vegetation, c) establishment or improvement of grasslands, d) establishment of woody crops . This measure also includes maintenance payments for agroforestry implemented during the 2014-22 period. However, the annual maintenance for agroforestry implemented by this measure is covered by AECM 6502.2. The agroforestry systems that the Autonomous Regions intend to establish are: Asturias (121 projects), Catalonia (160 projects), Galicia (1,250 ha), Community of Madrid (5 projects), Murcia (361 ha), and Navarre (475 ha).

Table 6. Investment measures (Articles 73-74) in Pillar II of the Spanish CAP Strategic Plan (2023-28). In bold: measures potentially related to agroforestry.

Code	Measure
6841.1	Productive Investment in agricultural holdings linked to mitigation of and adaptation to climate change, the efficient use of natural resources and animal welfare.
6841.2	Aid for investments in modernization and/or improvement of agricultural holdings
6842.1	Aid for investments with environmental objectives in the transformation, marketing and/or development of agri-food products.
6842.2	Aid for investments in transformation, marketing and/or product development agri-food
6843.1	Aid for investments in irrigation infrastructure with environmental objectives
6843.2	Aid for investments in agricultural infrastructure to promote competitiveness
6844	Non-productive investments in agricultural holdings linked to mitigation-adaptation to climate change, efficient use of natural resources and biodiversity
6864	Investment aid for agricultural diversification
6871	Non-productive investments in basic services in the natural environment
6872	Investments in basic services in rural areas
6881.1	Non-productive forest investments in reforestation and agroforestry systems
6881.2	Non-productive Forestry investments to prevent forest damage
6881.3	Non-productive investments in restoring forest damage
6881.4	Non-productive forest investments in silvicultural actions with environmental objectives
6883	Productive forest investments

- **INVEST 6844 - Aid for non-productive investments in agricultural holdings linked to mitigation of and adaptation to climate change, efficient use of natural resources and biodiversity.** It supports actions on: a) conservation and improvement of biodiversity, especially in the case of protected habitats and species, restoration of agricultural habitats of community interest, creation and maintenance of elements that create environmental heterogeneity; b) Conservation of the natural and/or ethnological landscape and its elements, how are the landscapes linked to agricultural practices. In Extremadura this measure has been implemented focused on the regeneration and improvement of pastures.
- **INVEST 6881.2 - Non-productive investments to prevent forest damage:** measure aimed at promoting sustainable forest management, increasing multifunctionality and adaptation to climate change, increasing and restoring the wooded forest area and also conserving and restoring agroforestry systems. These include, among other actions, forestry work and the use of livestock to prevent fires in forest masses, agricultural surfaces and linear infrastructures or the installation and improvement of pastures.
- **INVEST 6881.3 - Non-productive forest investments for forest damage restoration:** With the same objectives as 6881.2, this measure includes forestry treatments (clearing, thinning, resurfacing, treatment of residues), actions for erosion control, reforestation and associated infrastructure, actions for grazing management (boundaries, enclosures, arrangement or construction of livestock infrastructure) or actions for the improvement and conservation of biodiversity: arrangement or creation of water points with faunal interest, installation of refuges, etc.
- **INVEST 6881.4 - Non-productive investments in forestry actions with environmental objectives:** silvicultural actions that increase the stability and resilience of forest areas in the face of biotic and abiotic alterations, including: a) silvicultural management and improvement plans; b) forestry improvement and diversification actions; c) promoting and regulating the sustainable use and public use of forests; d) recovery and maintenance of the livestock trail network.
- **INVEST 6883 - Productive forest investments:** aid for the conservation and maintenance of all the productive potential of the forests, including investments for the transformation, mobilisation and marketing of forest products. The actions include: a) Management and improvement plans with productive purposes; b) Forestry actions to improve the economic value of forests: pruning, thinning and other treatments that improve the volume and quality of wood and other non-wood products

(cork, resin, pine nuts); afforestations and plantations with high-value species; c) Investments for the use, transformation, mobilisation and marketing of forest products: machinery and equipment, facilities, etc.

Other measures such as INVEST 6841.1 (Aid for productive investments in agricultural holdings linked to contributing to the mitigation-adaptation to climate change, efficient use of natural resources and animal welfare) and INVEST6864 (Investment aid for agricultural diversification) could also encourage agroforestry, although it is not explicitly mentioned.

Table 7 shows which Autonomous Communities have adopted each of the 13 Pillar II measures potentially applicable to agroforestry. Of these, an average of more than 7 have been activated for each Autonomous Community. The most widely adopted measures are the Forestry. Investments (6881, 6883). The two measures that include the agroforestry in their title (6502.2 and 6881.1) have been activated in 10 and 11 Autonomous Communities, respectively. All the Autonomous Communities have activated at least 4 of these outstanding measures. Castilla y León, Galicia and Navarra stand out, with at least 10 of these 13 measures activated.

The MAPA "[Balance PAC 2024](#)", gives summary information on CAP "investment" expenditure but does not refer to the specific codes mentioned above, making it difficult to check on key investments.

Table 7 Activation by Autonomous Community of Agro-environmental and Climate and Investment Measures identified as favourable to agroforestry systems. (Dalmau et al. 2024)

Measure	AN	AR	AS	IB	PV	CB	CM	CL	CN	CT	EX	GA	MD	MC	NC	RI	VC	Tot
6501.1 Integrated production				X	X				X		X							4
6501.2 Sustainable Crop Commitments	X			X	X		X	X	X	X		X			X	X		10
6501.3 Commitments to promote and sustainably manage pastures	X				X	X		X	X	X		X			X			8
6501.6 Maintenance or improvement of habitats and traditional agricultural activities that preserve biodiversity		X	X			X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X	X	11
6501.8 Practices for soil improvement and combating erosion		X						X	X						X			4
6502.1 Forest management commitments						X		X			X	X						4
6502.2 Forestry and systems maintenance commitments in agroforestry	X	X				X	X	X			X	X		X	X	X		10
6844 Aid for non-productive investments in agricultural holdings linked to mitigation-adaptation to climate change, efficient use of natural resources and biodiversity			X	X			X	X			X	X	X					7
6881.1 Non-productive forest investments in reforestation and agroforestry		X	X			X		X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		11
6881.2 Non-productive forest investments in prevention of forest damage	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	16
6881.3 Non-productive forest investments in forest damage restoration	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	15
6881.4 Non-productive forestry investments in forestry actions with environmental objectives	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	12
6883 Productive forestry investments	X		X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X			X		X	11
TOTAL	7	6	7	4	4	8	8	12	7	8	9	10	6	6	10	6	5	

AN: Andalusia; AR: Aragon; AS: Asturias; IB: The Balearic Islands; PV: Basque Country; CB: Cantabria; CM: Castile-La Mancha; CL: Castile and Leon; CN: Canaries; CT: Catalonia; EX: Extremature; GA: Galicia; MD: Community of Madrid; MC: Region of Murcia; NC: Foral Community of Navarre; RI: The Rioja; VC: Valencian Community

7. Agroforestry and CAP performance metrics

The Results (R), Output (O) and Impact (I) [indicators](#) are used by the Commission to measure the achievement of the objectives of the CAP as a whole. The most relevant to agroforestry are:

- **R.12 Adaptation to climate change:** percentage of Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) subject to subsidised commitments to improve adaptation to climate change. Up to 98,331 hectares will be committed to contribute to this result indicator (the organic farming area has not been computed)
- **R.14 Carbon storage in soils and biomass:** percentage of UAS subject to subsidised commitments to reduce emissions, or maintain and improve carbon storage (including permanent grasslands, permanent crops with permanent vegetation cover, and agricultural land in wetlands and peatlands). The general target value for Spain is 7,824,826 ha (i.e 32.1% of the UAA).
- **R.16 Climate-related investments:** percentage of agricultural holdings benefiting from CAP investment aid that contribute to adaptation to climate change and its mitigation, as well as to the production of renewable energy or biomaterials. The target value is 7.19% of farms.
- **R.17 Forested lands:** subsidised area for afforestation, agroforestry and reclamation. The result indicator for Spain is 38,967 ha, but no breakdown is provided between the three categories.
- **R.18 Investment aid for the forestry sector:** total investment to improve the performance of the forestry sector. The objective is €238.03 million.
- **R.19 Soil improvement and protection:** percentage of UAAs subject to beneficial aid commitments for soil management aimed at improving soil quality and biota (such as reduced tillage, soil cover with crops and crop rotation, including legumes). The number of hectares planned under these commitments is 10,536,866 ha (43.2% of the UAA).
- **R.25 Environmental performance in the livestock sector:** percentage of livestock units subject to subsidised commitments to improve environmental sustainability. The number of livestock units subject to these commitments is 307,415, which represents 2.13% of the total.
- **R.26 Investments related to natural resources:** percentage of agricultural holdings benefiting from CAP aid for productive and non-productive investments related to the protection of natural resources. The number of farms receiving relevant aid is 26,143, or 2.77% of the total.
- **R.30 Support for sustainable forest management:** percentage of forest land subject to commitments to support forest protection and management of ecosystem services. The number of hectares under this objective is 151,399 ha (0.62% of the total forest area).
- **R.31 Preservation of habitats and species:** percentage of UAAs subject to aid commitments that promote the conservation or recovery of biodiversity, including high natural value agricultural practices. The overall target value is 3,899,477 ha, or 16.0% of the UAA.
- **R.32 Investments related to biodiversity:** percentage of farms that receive CAP investment aid in favor of biodiversity. The general objective is 2,088 farms (0.22% of the total) that will receive the relevant aid.
- **R.34 Preservation of landscape elements:** percentage of UAA subject to subsidised commitments for the management of landscape elements, including hedges and trees. This result can also include the surface of “permanent crops”, so it could cover larger areas than those strictly considered “landscape elements”, according to the CAP Implementing Regulation. The UAA subject to financed commitments to manage landscape elements is 61,238 ha, which represents 0.25% of the total UAA (target value for this indicator).
- **O.14 Number of hectares (excluding forestry) or number of other units subject to environmental or climate commitments that go beyond mandatory requirements.** The total planned area is 20,587.953 ha, with a total expenditure allocation of €763,694,047.
- **O.15 Number of hectares (forestry) or number of other units subject to environmental or climate commitments that go beyond mandatory requirements.** Management commitments include 368,019 ha (5,000 units), with a financial allocation (total public expenditure of €7,763,175).
- **O.16 Maintenance payments for forestry and agroforestry:** The total planned area is 87,285 ha with a cost of €27,069,248, but no breakdown is provided between afforestation, restoration and reforestation.

Two Impact Indicators should also be highlighted: I.21. “percentage of agricultural land covered with landscape elements” and I.22. “crop diversity”. It is not clear when Member States will begin to provide data on Impact Indicators such as these.

Data on these Result, Output and Impact Indicators is not provided in the Spanish Annual Monitoring Report ([Balance PAC-24](#)), and only partially available through the Commission [Result Indicator Dashboard](#),

which amalgamates details on afforestation, reforestation, agroforestation and landscape features into a single indicator for R.17 (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #70](#) on "simplification of the CAP")

Based on the **Spanish CAP Annual Performance Report** (specifically the analysis of the *Balance PAC 2024* provided in the "Agroforestry systems in the Spanish CAP Strategic Plan" document), here is the information regarding the area funded and targets for the specified codes:

INVEST 6881.1 (Non-productive forest investments in reforestation and agroforestry systems)

- **Funded Area:** The report notes that the Annual Performance Report (*Balance PAC 2024*) provides summary information on investment expenses but **does not refer to specific codes**, which makes it "extremely difficult" to verify the exact area funded for this intervention.
- **Targets (Intended Establishment):** The Autonomous Communities have set the following targets for establishing agroforestry systems under this measure:
 - **Galicia:** 1,250 ha
 - **Navarre:** 475 ha
 - **Murcia:** 361 ha
 - **Catalonia:** 160 projects
 - **Asturias:** 121 projects
 - **Community of Madrid:** 5 projects

AECM 6502.2 (Commitments to maintain forestry and agroforestry systems)

- **Funded Area:** Similar to the investment measure, the specific funded area is not clearly broken down by code in the Annual Performance Report. The analysis highlights that the impact remains unclear unless the report specifies which AECM measures were applied to which parcels.
- **Targets:**
 - **Cantabria:** 500 ha.
 - **Extremadura and Galicia:** These regions have specific budgets for agroforestry systems under this measure, but the specific area targets are not indicated.

General Indicators For broader context, the CAP Strategic Plan sets a result indicator (**R.17 Forested lands**) for Spain of **38,967 ha** for afforestation, agroforestry, and reclamation combined, without a specific breakdown between the three categories

REC 5: Disaggregate information on tree-planting (R.17) to show afforestation, restoration, agroforestry and landscape features. In the CAP Annual Performance Report Result Indicator 17 is provided as a single aggregated value for the four types of tree planting above. This prevents information being available on agroforestry and is contrary to guidance in the CAP Basic Act and its Implementing Regulation.

8. Agroforestry in the Spanish LPIS System (SIGPAG)

Silvopasture is the most common form of agroforestry in Spain, and has two specific "Pasture" PA (Pasto con Arbolado) - pasture with scattered trees and PR - pasture with shrub layers which are grazed. The CSP (*Coeficiente de Subvencionabilidad de Pastos*) shows the eligibility of the parcel for basic payments discounting the area covered by dense impenetrable vegetation or steep slopes while acknowledging the grazeable area under the tree canopy. In silvoarable systems, as long as the tree density is low (e.g. <100 trees/ha), the trees are considered landscape features or scattered elements and do not affect eligibility. A parcel coded as FO is considered forest and will not receive basic payments. Trees in lines or small groups may also be recorded as landscape features and will be eligible in full for area payments.

9. Agroforestry stakeholder questionnaire responses

The EU Survey website was used to provide a [questionnaire](#) to contacts of the AgroForAdapt project in Spain and France. It is still open. A total of 127 responses were received from stakeholders in Spain by the end of October and the data are provisionally summarised in [EURAF Research Report #55](#). **The sector seems poised for significant expansion, yet is critically constrained by structural, administrative, and political barriers.**

The respondent cohort is dominated by a highly informed group of technicians, researchers, and consultants (75 respondents, or 59.1% of the total), indicating that the challenges and opportunities identified are based on deep knowledge of the system. While willingness to adopt agroforestry is high among farmer respondents, a significant portion (18 farmers, or 43.9% of the farmer cohort) make their adoption conditional upon improvements to subsidies and regulations. The analysis identifies the primary obstacles to adoption. These are not, as commonly assumed, cultural resistance from farmers; 'social pressure' and 'farmers being against' were the lowest-ranked barriers. Instead, the principal barriers are unambiguously political and administrative: a) "not supportive" regulatory framework (Top-ranked barrier; Score: 429). b) "Policy uncertainty on future grants" (Second-ranked barrier; Score: 420).

Stakeholders provided a clear mandate for reform. The highest-priority policy changes are not for new subsidies, but for fixing the existing administrative framework. This includes clarifying the "stacking" of payments (e.g., 'organic' + 'agroforestry' - Top-ranked policy; Score: 440), and creating new land use codes for "silvoarable" and "silvopastoral" systems within the Spanish Land Parcel Information System (LPIS), known as SIGPAC (Second-ranked policy; Score: 432).

The analysis uncovered a perverse incentive within the current Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) framework which disincentivized farmers from planting trees. Several respondents reported deliberately not declaring their agroforestry systems in SIGPAC to "not lose declarable [subsidy] area". The current system, designed for monocultures, penalizes integrated systems by potentially reclassifying land as "forestry" or reducing eligible areas, thus financially punishing the very farmers attempting to adopt sustainable practices. Further structural impediments include a "tenancy trap", where the short-term nature of land rental agreements makes long-term tree planting financially and legally unviable for tenants, and a significant "knowledge gap," with a lack of technical support and applied research for Spain's diverse bioregions. The following recommendations were made by respondents:

REC 6. Make all existing silvopastoral parcels (SIGPAC PA and PR codes) eligible for 100% area payments providing livestock units exceed the minimum legal threshold: Livestock numbers are held in IACS/SIGPAC along with parcel numbers on a holding⁷ - full area payments should be made if the livestock units exceed the legal density per ha.

REC 7. Make abandoned agricultural or forestry land, both within and outside SIGPAC, eligible for reclassification as silvopasture (PA and PR parcels) - providing that operators submit a livestock management plan showing that livestock density (*carga ganadera*) exceeds the legal threshold.

REC 8. Simplify administrative processes associated with agroforestry establishment and maintenance grants. - for example there are often major delays in reimbursement for the costs of a Forest Engineer to design the plan which could be covered quickly in an annual Ecoscheme.

REC 9. Develop "Knowledge Transfer Hubs" or "Agroforestry Living Labs" where farmers can see profitable demonstrations of new machinery and techniques: this will bridge the gap between research and practice, and between forestry and agricultural technical support systems and training colleges

⁷ see EURAF Research Report #105 "Livestock density compliance tools in the Spanish IACS System"

10. Agroforestry and environmental policies beyond the CAP

While most policies relevant to farmers relate to the CAP and the CAP Strategic Plan there are several regulations and initiatives which will have increasing importance in the future, and which will influence policies in the CAP 2028-34

10.1 Agroforestry in the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation

EU Regulation 2018/841 describes methods to be used by Member States in calculating GHG emissions from the LULUCF sector. It mentions that *“The development of innovative and sustainable technologies and practices, including agroecology and agroforestry, can increase the role of the LULUCF sector in mitigating and adapting to climate change, as well as strengthening the productivity and resilience of the sector.”*

The updated National Energy and Climate Plan for Spain ([September 2024](#)) outlines several measures related to forestry and agroforestry management:

- **Sustainable Forest Management:** Promoting forest management practices that enhance carbon sequestration, maintain and improve forest health and resilience, and sustainably supply wood and non-wood forest products. This includes measures to increase the area under sustainable forest management certification.
- **Afforestation and Reforestation:** Implementing programs to increase forest cover on degraded or non-forested land, thereby enhancing carbon sinks and biodiversity. The plan includes specific targets for afforestation and reforestation areas.
- **Agroforestry Systems:** Encouraging the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes to enhance carbon sequestration, improve soil health, and provide other environmental benefits.
- **Prevention and Management of Forest Fires:** Strengthening measures for the prevention, early detection, and efficient management of forest fires, which are a significant source of GHG emissions and can severely impact forest carbon stocks. This includes investing in fire prevention infrastructure, improving coordination among relevant authorities, and promoting public awareness.
- **Restoration of Degraded Land:** Implementing measures to restore degraded land, including peatlands and wetlands, which can be significant sources of emissions when degraded but can act as carbon sinks when healthy.
- **Sustainable Use of Wood Products:** Promoting the use of sustainably sourced wood products as a substitute for more carbon-intensive materials, thereby contributing to carbon storage in harvested wood products.
- **Climate Change Adaptation in Forestry:** Implementing measures to enhance the resilience of forests to the impacts of climate change, such as droughts, pests, and diseases, to ensure the long-term sustainability of their carbon sequestration potential.
- **Monitoring and Reporting:** Strengthening the systems for monitoring and reporting GHG emissions and removals from the LULUCF sector to ensure accurate accounting and tracking of progress towards targets

REC 10. Implement an emergency tree planting and assisted regeneration programme to help meet LULUCF targets. Spain has a commitment to provide -43.635 Mt of net removals of CO₂ in 2030 and much more in 2040 and 2050. Targets given in the National Energy and Climate Plan (*Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima - PNIIEC-2*) need an emergency tree planting programme, much in excess of current levels to help meet Spain's almost impossible LULUCF goal of -43.635 M tonnes CO₂ by 2030.

Annex II of the LULUCF Regulation ([DG CLIMA, 2023](#)) indicates that Spain will change its definition of “Forest Land” in 2028, at least for the purposes of GHG reporting. The minimum size of the forest plot will remain at 1.0 ha and the minimum tree height at 3 m, but the minimum tree canopy coverage will decrease from 20% to 10%. This change may make it necessary to reclassify the area considered “forest” and recalculate carbon absorption for each year since 1990, but it is not clear if it will be accompanied by a reclassification of “forest” plots in SIGPAC⁸.

⁸ It should be noted that the SIGPAC system is one of the few in the EU that has integrated agricultural and forestry cadastres. Most other countries register forest plots in their SIP system (Spanish CAP implementation only takes place if payments have been made on them under Pillar II of the CAP... for example, for afforestation of agricultural land) .

10.2 Agroforestry in the EUDR Regulation.

The multifunctionality of agroforestry, while a significant strength, also presents a policy challenge. Because it integrates elements of agriculture, forestry, and environmental conservation, which cut across traditional sectoral policy divides. This necessitates robust inter-sectoral coordination among different Spanish ministries and agencies at various administrative levels to ensure coherent policy development and implementation. The problem is illustrated by the study of EU "forest" classifications conducted by EURAF in its Policy Briefing "*Defining Forests and Agroforests in the EU*" ([EURAF Policy Briefing #15](#)). In the Spanish context this looked, in 10m pixel detail, at the region of Extremadura (4.16 million ha): concluding that the area of "forest use" according to the forestry department ([MITECO 2021](#)) is 2.87 Mha, while the JRC global map of forests (for EUDR purposes) suggests 0.97 Mha and the MAPA-SIGPAC system indicates only 0.20 Mha. Most of the difference is due to the area of "*pastizal con arboles*" (1,150,280 ha) and "*pastizal con arbustos*" (784,854 ha) (Table 8). The Spanish national greenhouse gas Inventory splits the difference by classifying the former as "forest" and the latter as "grassland".

Table 8: Area (ha) identified as "forest" in the EU JRC Forest Observatory for Extremadura and the distribution of this total forest area (968,437 ha) between 5 Land Use categories identified in the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (SIGPAC)

Uso de Suelo (ha)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	200,902	79,607	280,509
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	401,975	748,305	1,150,280
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	204,386	580,468	784,854
SIGPAC Pastizal (PS)	14,392	398,161	412,553
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	146,782	1,388,441	1,535,224
Total	968,437	3,194,983	4,163,421

Uso de Suelo (%)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	20.7%	2.5%	6.7%
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	41.5%	23.4%	27.6%
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	21.1%	18.2%	18.9%
SIGPAC Pastizal (PS)	1.5%	12.5%	9.9%
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	15.2%	43.5%	36.9%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 8 indicates that a clarified interpretation of the 1962 "Ley de Montes" ([485/62](#)) is needed for consistent reporting across a number of recent regulations (LULUCF, NNR; CRCF, EUDR etc). Article 4(1) of the *Ley de Montes* indicates: "*Se entiende por monte o terreno forestal la tierra en que vegetan especies arbóreas, arbustivas de matorral o herbáceas, sea espontáneamente o procedan de siembra o plantación, siempre que no sean características del cultivo agrícola o fueren objeto del mismo.*"⁹

The 2003 "Ley de Montes" [43/2003](#) includes a similar definition in Article 5(1) (Concepto de monte" that: "A los efectos de esta ley, se entiende por monte todo terreno en el que vegetan especies forestales arbóreas, arbustivas, de matorral o herbáceas, sea espontáneamente o procedan de siembra o plantación, que cumplan o puedan cumplir funciones ambientales, protectoras, productoras, culturales, paisajísticas o recreativas." For the purposes of this law, woodland is understood to mean any land on which forest tree, shrub, scrub or herbaceous species grow, either spontaneously or from sowing or planting, which fulfil or may fulfil environmental, protective, productive, cultural, landscape or recreational functions.

⁹Forest land or woodland is defined as land on which tree, shrub or herbaceous species grow, either spontaneously or as a result of sowing or planting, provided that they are not characteristic of agricultural cultivation or are not the object of such cultivation.

The failings of the Ley de Montes definition are discussed in the Spanish Forest Strategy ([MITECO 2003, p17](#)), which points out that the Forest Acts of Catalonia, Navarra, Andalucia, Valencia, La Rioja and Madrid have their own definitions of “forest land”, which depart from the national law. Furthermore, Spain has provided a definition of “forests” to the UNFCCC and to the EU in Annex II of the LULUCF Regulation ([2023/839](#)) which defines forest in terms of the three international criteria recognised in the UNFCCC Marrakesh accords ([UNFCCC 2001](#)): minimum parcel size, minimum tree crown cover and minimum tree height.¹⁰ The precise definition of “forest” has become very important for landowners and operators in the context of the EU Deforestation Regulation.

The EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) ([2023/1115](#)) will come into effect on 30/12/2026. It imposes strict rules of due diligence to all companies wishing to place affected products on the European market, or to export them, and applies to importers and producers of key products in EU Member States. These products (cattle derivatives, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, soya, wood, and rubber) must be geolocated and accompanied by a due diligence statement confirming that they have not been produced on land which was deforested after 31st December 2000. The EUDR specifically excludes agroforestry areas from the definition of “forests”, few countries worldwide or in Europe have effective maps of “Agroforestry”

The Ministry of Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO) confirmed in comments to PEFC Spain ([11.8.25](#)) that: *Los productos elaborados con materias primas que han sido producidas en parcelas de uso agrícola o agroforestal también deberán cumplir con el EUDR. Por tanto, la madera extraída de árboles en las dehesas y el ganado vacuno de dehesas sí están regulados por el EUDR. Hay que destacar que la condición de que los productos pertinentes estén libres de deforestación en EUDR será más fácil de demostrar en parcelas agrícolas precisamente debido a su uso agrario, donde no puede haber deforestación. Por ejemplo, en parcelas con un uso agrícola dentro de la PAC se podría utilizar la documentación de la PAC asociada a la parcela para demostrar que dicha parcela ya tenía uso agrario en 2020.*¹¹

REC 11. Confirm, for the purposes of the EUDR, that all SIGPAC codes PA and PR count as agroforestry. MITECO has already clarified that parcels having SIGPAC silvopastoral codes in December 2020 cannot be subject to “deforestation”. It should be further clarified that this applies to PA and PR parcels, whatever their current CSP.

10.3 Agroforestry in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework

The EU is developing a Carbon Removals Certification Framework, and carbon farming methodologies for “agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils”; “afforestation” and “peatland rewetting” (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #20](#)). This will offer great opportunities for financial support to agroforestry beyond the 5-6 years when CAP incentives are available, but will also bring requirements for robust monitoring and creation of a management plan to guarantee biodiversity benefits and “no significant harm” to other environmental indicators.

In addition to the mentions of agroforestry in Spanish National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) 2021-2030 (see above), there exists in Spain a *Registro de Huella de Carbono, Compensación y Proyectos de Absorción de CO2* was established by Royal Decree in 2014, and is a public, voluntary registry managed by the Spanish Office for Climate Change (MAGRAMA 2016). This is used for domestic Land Use, Land-Use

¹⁰ Currently for Spain these are: minimum area 1 ha, minimum tree crown cover 20%, minimum tree height 3m. From the GHG inventory of 2028 (for 2026) onwards the tree crown cover threshold will be 10%.

¹¹ Products made from raw materials that have been produced on agricultural or agroforestry land must also comply with the EUDR. Therefore, wood extracted from trees in pastures and cattle from pastures are regulated by the EUDR. It should be noted that the condition that the relevant products are deforestation-free in the EUDR will be easier to demonstrate on agricultural land precisely because of its agricultural use, where there can be no deforestation. For example, on land used for agricultural purposes under the CAP, CAP documentation associated with the land could be used to demonstrate that the land was already in agricultural use in 2020.

Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) activities, and it currently limited to land-use projects of two types: a) afforestation and reforestation on land that has been without forest cover since at least 1989, and b) the restoration of forest areas affected by fire. The registry imposes strict requirements, including a minimum project area of 1 hectare, a 30-year permanence commitment, and the mandatory use of a specific calculation methodology provided by the registry itself, which is based on IPCC guidelines.

The Spanish Forest Strategy (EFE) 2050 ([MITECO 2022](#)), includes a commitment to Increase the carbon sink capacity of forest areas. Achieve at least the level of climate neutrality envisaged for 2050 in EU legislation - with an increase of 7.04 MtCO₂eq in net absorption through afforestation, 4.34 MtCO₂eq through the improved forest management and 0.54 MtCO₂eq through the promotion of agroforestry systems and the regeneration of pastureland.

Regional measures, for example a) the Climate Credit System of Catalonia, which articulates a system of forest climate credits (which integrate the effect of forestry practices on carbon, water and biodiversity) and agricultural land climate credits, in the articulation phase; In the preamble of this Government Agreement, agroforestry systems are explicitly mentioned, so it is expected that these practices can benefit from this system; (b) the voluntary carbon credit market of Galicia, which is in the formulation phase and is expected to include sustainable forest management measures, silvopastoralism and (agro)forestation.

REC 12. Plan CAP support for agroforestry in a way that is “stackable” with long-term carbon credits. CAP interventions, including ecoschemes (planning), investment measures (planting) and agro-environment-climate measures (5-year maintenance “prima”) can be a precursor for entry into agroforestry carbon farming certification. The EU DGCLIMA has already clarified that this is possible, providing that the operator submits with the application for carbon certification a “financial additionality budget” showing that the project wouldn't be viable without **both** CAP and CRCF funding.

10.4 Agroforestry in the Nature Restoration Regulation

All Member States are required to send a draft Nature Restoration Plan to Brussels by 1.9.2026. The most recent Habitats Directive reporting for Spain showed that 60% of habitats were in an unfavourable (poor or bad) condition, with more than 70% for forest habitats. The Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) suggests biodiversity indicators for agricultural and forest diversity. One of the three agricultural biodiversity indicators is “Share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features (HDLF)”, and there are difficulties distinguishing HDLF from “ordinary” landscape features recorded in the CAP - see Commission Notice [C/2025/980](#). Apparently, the NRR definition of HDLF excludes “productive trees” unless they form part of “sustainable agroforestry systems” but does leave the option for Member States to propose their own indicators. We therefore suggest that Spain should define “high-diversity landscape features” in a way that matches existing “elementos de paisaje” in SIGPAC.

REC 13. Ensure that the national and regional Nature Restoration Plans use the existing CAP definition and statistics on Landscape Features. Confusion has been created by the EU Nature Regulation Regulation (2024/1991) talking of “high diversity landscape features” without providing a workable definition of what this means. SIGPAC is already recording landscapes. SIGPAC - MAPA and MITECO should confirm that only a single integrated indicator is needed.

10.5 Agroforestry, Nature Credits and Water Resilience

Agroforestry systems offer a wide range of ecosystem services, include enhanced climate mitigation, climate adaptation, improved biodiversity by providing habitats for various species, including pollinators and natural pest controllers; protection of soil resources against erosion through the stabilizing effect of tree roots, and improved water cycles and quality See “*Agricultural Trees for Resilient Landscapes: a Vision for European Agroforestry*” ([EURAF 2025](#)). These benefits could be costed and included in agri-environmental incentives

through methodologies being developed in the Commission's "Roadmap Towards Nature Credits" (7.7.25 - [COM 2025-374](#)) and "Water Resilience Strategy" (4.6.25 - [COM 2025-280](#)).

Beyond environmental advantages, agroforestry offers substantial socio-economic benefits: it allows the diversification of farm income through products like timber, fruits, nuts, and fodder, alongside traditional agricultural outputs. This diversification can enhance the economic resilience of farms, particularly in the face of climate change and market volatility. Agroforestry also supports rural development by creating employment opportunities and maintaining diverse rural landscapes). The estimated area of dehesa-agroforestry in Spain varies between studies, but could be as high as 5.8 million ha (Joffre, Rambal, and Ratte 1999; Gaspar et al. 2008) This is the largest area of wood pasture habitat in Europe, and is a crucial example for other countries of this traditional, multifunctional agroforestry system.

To calculate the environmental impact of agricultural practices open and up-to-date access to parcel based agricultural information is needed. The Spanish SIGPAC system is one of the most modern, open and comprehensive datasets of land use information in the EU. Until recently Spain was only "largely compliant" with the EU High Value Datasets Regulation (2023) since some regions (e.g. Castilla y Leon) provide data with "non-commercial" restrictions on its reuse ([EURAF Research Report #8](#)). However at the end of 2025 MAPA provided a new API service which is fully compliant with the HVD Regulation.

REC 14. Develop "Agroforestry" Product Certification. Create a government-backed label (or add to existing organic labels) that certifies products come from agroforestry parcels, allowing consumers to pay a premium for the ecosystem services provided, similar to the existing Montonera scheme for acorn-fed ham.

REC 15: Research the use of virtual collars for cattle, sheep and goats in automated systems connected to SIGPAC. Collars will provide proof of which parcels are grazed and can incentivize those areas flagged as "high fire risk". Partial collaring will often be sufficient.

REC 16. Provide special tax regimes (REGAP), direct payments (PES) and CAP exemptions for shepherds operating in high fire-load SIGPAC parcels . Especially in association with local fire management plans.

REC 17. Give nature credit (PES) supplements to increase the value of tree-planting grants for Municipalities with high "tree-desert" indices. Information on tree desert indices can be included annually as a flag in each SIGPAC parcel using from Copernicus 10m tree cover density data.

REC 18. Support Producer Cooperatives: Provide tax incentives for small agroforestry producers to form cooperatives that can aggregate volume and process biomass/timber locally, capturing more value.

REC 19. Adapt Slaughter Regulations: Modify sanitary regulations to allow small-scale, mobile, or on-farm slaughtering facilities, reducing costs and improving animal welfare for extensive livestock farms.

10.6 Agroforestry in the national and regional climate adaptation strategies

The most recent adaptation strategy for Spain is the *Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático* (PNACC) 2021-2030 ([MITECO 2021](#)). It is a basis for an "Programa de Trabajo" 2021-25 ([MITECO 2022](#)) and an *Evaluación de Riesgos e Impactos derivados del Cambio Climático 2025-30*. None of these documents specifically mention agroforestry, although they do stress the importance of increasing "sumideros de carbono" (carbon sinks) and tree planting. Agroforestry and dehesas are specifically mentioned, however, in the "Plan Extremeño Integrado de Energía y Clima 2021-2030" ([Junta de Extremadura 2020](#)), and the

“Estratégico de Cambio Climático para Castilla la Mancha 2020-2030” ([Junta CLM 2018](#)), but not in the “Programa Andaluz de Adaptación al Cambio Climático” ([Junta de Andalucía 2012](#)). The new “Plan de Trabajo 2026-30” is due to go for consultation in early 2026, and it is hoped that this makes greater mention of agroforestry.¹²

REC 20. Include agroforestry in the Adaptation Strategies of all Autonomous Regions (CCAA). The Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático (PNACC-2) was approved in 2020 and some regional strategies were written long before that. The PNACC second work programme (2026-2030) has not yet been finalised, with public consultation expected to start shortly. The agroforestry community should press for clear targets in the establishment and regeneration of large areas to agroforestry.

11. Agroforestry SWOT-A analysis

Available in English [HERE](#) and Spanish [HERE](#)

11.1 Strengths

1. **The largest agroforestry area in Europe.** It covers at least 7.5 Mha, most of which is eligible for area-based payments. This is matched by a growing number of people, projects and institutions active in generation and transfer of knowledge and advice on agroecology, including agroforestry systems.
2. **High Nature Value (HNV) Heritage.** The Spanish Dehesa is a globally recognized natural heritage system. It is deeply rooted in cultural identity, along with other age-old landscapes and elements such as transhumance routes.
3. **Recognition in the CAP Strategic Plan (PEPAC).** The national planning document explicitly highlights the role of agroforestry for multiple ecosystem services: climate change adaptation and mitigation, soil, water and biodiversity protection; cultural and recreational services.
4. **Premium Product Reputation.** Products derived from *Dehesas*, such as *Jamón Ibérico* (acorn-fed ham), hold prestigious “Protected Designations of Origin” (PDO) labels and can achieve high market prices.
5. **Fire Prevention.** Grazing livestock significantly reduces fuel loads in wooded areas, decreasing the vulnerability to large wildfires at landscape level. Successful initiatives are engaging farmers, shepherds, technical personnel, public administrations and local communities.
6. **Resource Efficiency.** Trees provide shade and fodder in summer (when herbaceous pasture may not be available) and shelter in winter, reducing stress on livestock and the need to supplement their feed.
7. **Resilience to Poor Soils.** Agroforestry systems in Spain often utilize acidic, shallow, or rocky soils that are unsuitable for intensive agriculture, turning marginal land into productive assets of high environmental value.
8. **Soil Conservation & C Sequestration.** Tree roots prevent erosion and increase water infiltration, which is critical in Spain’s semi-arid regions threatened with desertification. Agroforestry (both silvoarable and silvopastoral) captures significantly more C than treeless monocultures, contributing to the demanding LULUCF climate goals.
9. **Diversified Risk.** Mediterranean agroforestry producers rely on multiple income streams (livestock, crops, fruit, timber, firewood...), so they are less vulnerable to price drops in an individual product.

¹² See “Spanish Climate Adaptation Strategies 2023-2030”. [EURAF Research Report #104](#)

10. **Regional Flexibility.** Regional variations in agricultural and carbon interventions are common in Spain. In percentage expenditure terms, the top ones are: Galicia, Madrid, Asturias, Cantabria for fire prevention and restoration; b) Extremadura, Andalusia and Castilla-La Mancha for agro-silvo-pastoralism; c) Euskadi, Galicia, Castilla y Leon for sustainable forest management; d) Galicia, Andalusia and Catalonia for climate credits.

11.2 Weaknesses

1. **La Seca oak syndrome and natural regeneration problems.** This devastating dieback disease is caused by the pathogen *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, and, together with the threat which grazing poses to natural regeneration, threaten the long-term viability of the Dehesa.
2. **Transition stage.** Establishing new trees is a costly investment, especially in Mediterranean conditions, that can take decades to generate net profit to the farmer, despite the many societal and environmental advantages..
3. **Poor rural demographics.** The average age of farmers is high, and the share of tenant farmers is growing. This leads to less interest in adopting practices with long pay-back periods. In the deep interior of Spain depopulation is still accelerating¹³. Yet, young people willing to innovate often have poor access to the land.
4. **Complex Management.** Managing interaction between trees, crops and animals requires technical skills and labour inputs which may not be available. Machinery may be more suited to monocultures than mixtures, and the segregation between agricultural and forestry training schools makes it difficult to ensure that farmers and landowners are adequately trained.
5. **Bureaucratic Hurdles.** The complexity of agricultural interventions (with the Spanish PEPAC extending over 3,200 pages and varying from region to region) makes it difficult to understand the details of potential support measures. Tree planting schemes must be submitted by a forest technician, but these costs are only partially reimbursable, often after a long delay. The application is particularly difficult for innovative, complex proposals. Silvopastoral annual area payments are not guaranteed because of the difficulties proving to a satellite that the understorey is being grazed.
6. **Fragmented Supply Chains and weak markets.** The diversity of products obtained in agroforestry farms, and the absence of clear regional or quality labels (apart from *jamón de bellota*) hampers the options to market quality products at a premium price.
7. **Information gaps.** The lack of statistics on the area of new and existing agroforestry or landscape features, and inclusion of most *monte* in the “forest” definition, contributes to a lack of awareness of the potential of agroforestry among the general public and the non-dehesa agricultural sector outside. Demonstration systems are needed with a wider range of tree, crop and animal species and varieties.
8. **Legal and regulatory blurring.** The rules affecting agroforestry indicators are unclear: there is no clear legal threshold of tree size to be used when the 100 trees/ha limit is applied to ensure eligibility for area payments. Many Pillar II measures which could support agroforestry do not mention it explicitly or cover a wide range of interventions, diluting the potential support. “Landscape-features” implementation is poorly regulated, as some of the dimensions are confusing: for example small woodlands (copses) cannot be “landscape features” if they are bigger than 0.3 ha, but they cannot be “forest” unless they are larger than 1ha.
9. **Implementation of “landscape-features” (BCAM).** This land-use category was introduced in 2023 into SIGPAC to meet the needs of CAP “Enhanced Conditionality”, but the EU Simplification Regulation (2023/2831), in the same year, removed the need for strict monitoring of landscape feature area thresholds. Individual hedges, tree lines, and small groups of trees still need to be protected by farmers, but the obligations on farmers to record these areas are unclear.

¹³ e.g. Zamora, León, Palencia, Soria, Salamanca, Ávila, Ourense, Lugo, Teruel, Cáceres, Badajoz.

10. **Lack of quality, hardened and improved, tree seedlings and cuttings for afforestation and agroforestation.** According to the National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) and Forest Strategy (EFE 2050), Spain aims to plant 20,000 ha per year between 2025-30 and bring 100,000 ha annually of new forest area under full management. The supply of “forest reproductive material” from the nursery sector may not be sufficient to meet these needs, particularly given the extra-high quality needed for agroforestry planting at wide-spacing.

11.3 Opportunities

1. **Carbon farming markets.** New EU certifications for carbon removals could pay farmers for the C stored in their trees and soil, creating a new income stream, particularly for the huge areas of Spain with zero trees and low soil C levels. These markets might also help add value to pruning residues, early thinnings and biochar.
2. **New incentive measures.** The 2023-2027 CAP includes specific eco-schemes, investment and agri-environmental interventions that financially reward agroforestry and woody landscape features. Spain implements Pillar II schemes differently in each region, and this flexibility should be a strength: particularly for provinces in which agricultural land is almost completely treeless.
3. **Growing interest in agroecology.** The number of farmers, entities and research units interested in agroecology in general, and on agroforestry in particular, has grown steadily in recent years, with a parallel increase of demonstration sites and first-hand data. The *Comunidad de Sistemas Agroforestales y Cultivos Mixtos* ([link](#)), with nearly 200 members, is an example of this trend.
4. **Rural Tourism.** "Agrotourism" is booming and visitors will pay to stay in traditional farmhouses, watch cork harvesting, or experience agroforestry landscapes and diversity.
5. **Digitalization.** The process to appeal against the LIDAR-based calculation of the *Coeficiente de Sувencionabilidad de Pastos* (CSP) is based on time-consuming geo-tagged pictures. The track-logs produced with GPS collars would simplify this process. Regions like Navarra, Asturias, and Andalusia have launched pilot programs where virtual fencing data is being analyzed to update the "Pasture Maps". Collars can also help manage rotational grazing systems.
6. **Emerging funding opportunities.** Growing availability of public and private funding mechanisms to support actions favourable to climate change adaptation and mitigation impact and to ecosystem services (soil, water, biodiversity), e.g. through carbon and nature credits or voluntary sector green labels such as Ramats de foc / Flocks of Fire; FireWine / FireProducts).
7. **Integrated wildfire management opportunities:** there is a growing body of knowledge on fire-smart landscapes planning. In this context, silvopastoralism is a tool with high social acceptance and there is a growing demand to restore and grazing activities on forest areas which were abandoned in recent decades.
8. **Consensus on the need for a change in the agricultural model :** the crisis of conventional agriculture in Spain, which in many cases is not delivering viable results at an economic or environmental level, should lead to the introduction of more integrated approaches, such as agroforestry.
9. **Greater flexibility in calculating the CSP¹⁴.** The opportunity for Member States to identify grazable trees and shrubs in their national definitions of permanent pasture was used in only a modest way by Spain. It increased the eligible area of grassland (CSP) by 4.1%. There was an opportunity to go further.
10. **Greater sharing of lessons learnt amongst farmers and researchers.** Submeasure 8.2 “Creation and maintenance of agroforestry systems” was activated in six communities, although with a low

¹⁴ Coeficiente de Subvencionabilidad de Pastos

uptake (2.2% of the planned €91.5 M budget). Farmers in these communities are a great resource of experience, and their experiences and options should be recorded

11.4 Threats

1. **Climate Change Acceleration.** Mediterranean areas are suffering climate change impacts (rising temperatures, heat waves, pest attacks, droughts, extreme storms, forest fires). 74% of Spanish territory is at risk of desertification, making tree planting and regeneration more difficult. The summer of 2025 was the most destructive forest fire season in Spain in 30 years. The extreme heatwave created "sixth-generation" fires¹⁵ that were nearly impossible to stop, and which even damaged silvopastoral systems.
2. **Increased competition for land.** The expansion of solar farms and intensive and super-intensive farming systems (like super-intensive olive and avocado groves) compete for land and water resources, indicating that intensive management is needed even in agroforestry.
3. **Loss of family farms:** the crisis of the family farming model will keep increasing tenant farming and land accumulation in investment groups, with limited interest in long-term investments or in ameliorating local natural resources and landscapes. 40% of farm owners are over 65. As the old generation passes away without successors, the knowledge of how to manage some complex agroecosystems is being lost.
4. **Increasing market volatility.** Global fluctuations in grain and feed prices can make extensive livestock raising unviable if the farm cannot be self-sufficient in food. Livestock feed prices in Spain increased by 56% between 2019 and the peak in 2022, making many livestock farms unviable.
5. **Increasing policy uncertainty.** Changes in CAP definitions or regional regulations can suddenly make a farm ineligible for crucial subsidies, causing financial chaos especially in systems that are planned in the mid and long term. Even in the current CAP 2023-27 period changes have been made through a succession of Omnibus Regulations, including in GAEC1 (permanent grassland), GAEC2 (wetlands), GAEC4 (buffer strips), GAEC5 (tillage management), GAEC 6 (minimum soil cover), GAEC7 (crop rotation), GAEC8 (landscape features), GAEC9 (natura 2000).
6. **Continuing inertia in the land-sector.** This resistance includes owners, tenants, administrators, farming unions, agrobusinesses (agrochemicals, machinery, veterinary, land-owning investment groups). The current model has been shaped by actors who dislike profound changes in the production model, including types of agroforestry which they are not familiar with.
7. **Greater conflicts with wildlife.** The recovery of wolf populations in Northern Spain creates conflict with extensive livestock farmers, which must be addressed with better regulation. Furthermore the increased density of ungulates (roe deer, red deer, wild boar) increases the risk and cost of planting trees.
8. **Reduction in extensive livestock farming.** In the last 10 years, 20-30% of livestock farms, the vast majority of them extensive, have been lost in favor of an intensive model with high health risks and high environmental impact.
9. **Regulatory Rigidity.** Hygiene and sanitary regulations designed for industrial farms are often applied to extensive systems, creating impossible compliance costs for family farming. Emerging pest outbreaks (e.g. BSE and avian flu) make things even harder for small producers.

¹⁵ Traditional fires are driven by wind and terrain. Sixth-generation fires are driven by convective energy. They are so intense that they create their own weather systems, making them effectively impossible to extinguish until they run out of fuel or the atmosphere shifts.

12. Recommendations for ACTION

1. **Use a less restrictive and more transparent approach to calculating the “Coeficiente de Subvencionabilidad de los Pastos (CSP).** MAPA and Autonomous Regions (CCAA) should agree on a list of grazable shrubs and recognise that LIDAR gives a poor estimate of palatability of shrub vegetation. The 2026 changes in NDVI calculation discriminate against grazing on shrubs, meaning that agroforestry farmers will inevitably face a long appeal process and have to provide geolocated photos.
2. **Clarify the regulations affecting Landscape Features.** It is necessary to find a formula that allows: i) accounting and recording of these landscape features; ii) incentives for their establishment; iii) sustainable management; iv) productive use - including pruning, pollarding, firewood and organic fertilization. The European Regulation on the Simplification of the CAP (2024/1468) has introduced confusion regarding landscape features as well as simplification.
3. **Create a La Seca Task Force.** The risk posed by “la Seca” *Phytophthora cinnamomi* to oak dehesas in Spain is grave, and a national “Task Force” is needed to fund a coordinated, cross-regional action plan - focusing on control, mycorrhizal associations and breeding/selection for resistance.
4. **Use SIGPAC to give parcel by parcel information on CAP intervention codes.** MAPA should list which ecoscheme, agri-environment, and investment measure codes were implemented in which SIGPAC parcels, to allow the eventual impacts to be evaluated.
5. **Disaggregate information on tree-planting (R.17) to show afforestation, restoration, agroforestry and landscape features.** In the CAP Annual Performance Report Result Indicator 17 is provided as a single aggregated value for the four types of tree planting above. This makes it impossible to determine the new area of these systems.agroforestry, contravening the guidelines of the Basic Law of the CAP and its Implementing Regulation.
6. **Make all current silvopastoral parcels (PA and PR) eligible for 100% area payments providing livestock units exceed a minimum density.** Livestock numbers per holding are held in IACS/SIGPAC along with parcel areas: it should be made easier for farmers to demonstrate that for each parcel that their grazing animals exceed the required density per ha.
7. **Make it easier for historical agricultural land which is now classed as matorral (MT) or forest (FO) in SIGPAC to be reclassified silvopasture (PA or PR) -** providing that operators submit a livestock management plan showing that livestock density (*carga ganadera*) exceeds the required threshold, and that their parcels were were historically in agricultural use.¹⁶.
8. **Simplify administrative processes associated with agroforestry establishment and maintenance grants.** For example there are often major delays in reimbursement for the costs of a Forest Engineer to design the plan which could be covered quickly in an annual Ecoscheme
9. **Promote agroforestry associations.** Knowledge transfer hubs and living laboratories on agroforestry systems can bridge the gap between research and practice, and between forestry and agricultural technical support systems and training colleges.
10. **Implement an emergency agroforestry tree planting and regeneration programme.** Spain has a commitment to provide 43.675 Mt of net removals of CO₂ in 2030 and even more in 2040 and 2050. Targets given in the National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC-2) need an urgent tree planting programme/regeneration programme - with agroforestry playing a decisive role.
11. **Confirm that the SIGPAC codes for “pastizal con arboles” and pastizal con arbustos” count as agroforestry for the purposes of the EUDR.** MITECO has already clarified that parcels having a

¹⁶ Old aerial photos and surveys (e.g. 1997 vuelo SIGPAC, Corine 1990/2000 map, SIOSE 2005) could be made available through SIGPAC for this purpose

PA and PR designation in December 2020 will not be considered to have suffered “deforestation”. It should be further clarified that this applies to PA and PR parcels - whatever their current eligibility for grant payment (i.e. CSP).

12. **Ensure that CAP support for agroforestry is “stackable” with long-term carbon credits.** CAP interventions, including ecoschemes (for planning), investment measures (for planting) and agro-environment-climate measures (for maintenance “prima”) can be a “starter-pack” for agroforestry carbon farming certification. The EU CRCF draft Delegated Act has already clarified that this may be possible, providing that the operator submits a “financial additionality budget” showing that the project wouldn't be viable without both CAP and CRCF funding.
13. **Ensure that the national and regional Nature Restoration Plans use the existing CAP definition and statistics on Landscape Features.** Confusion has been created by the EU Nature Regulation Regulation (2024/1991) talking of “high diversity landscape features” without providing a workable definition of what this means. SIGPAC is already recording landscape SIGPAC - MAPA and MITECO should confirm that only a single integrated indicator is needed.
14. **Develop "Agroforestry" Product Certification.** Create a government-backed label or certificate certifying products from agroforestry parcels, allowing consumers to pay a premium for the ecosystem services provided - in a similar to the existing *Montonera* scheme for acorn-fed ham.
15. **Support innovations that promote the economic and technical viability of agroforestry systems and the efficiency of their regulation.** For example, support research the use of virtual collars for cattle, sheep and goats in automated systems connected to SIGPAC.. Collars will provide proof of which parcels are grazed and can incentivize use of those areas flagged as “high fire risk”. Partial collaring of lead animals will often be sufficient.
16. **Provide special tax regimes (REGAP), direct payments (PES) and CAP exemptions for farmers and shepherds operating in high fire-load areas.** In association with local fire management plans.
17. **Give nature credit (PES) supplements to increase the value of tree-planting grants for Municipalities with high “tree-desert” indices.** Information on “tree desert indices” can be included annually as a flag in each SIGPAC parcel using data from the Copernicus 10m resolution Tree Cover Density product.
18. **Support Producer Cooperatives.** Provide tax incentives for small agroforestry producers to form cooperatives that can aggregate volume and process biomass/timber locally, capturing more value.
19. **Adapt Slaughter Regulations.** Modify sanitary regulations to allow small-scale, mobile, or on-farm slaughtering facilities, reducing costs and improving animal welfare for extensive livestock farms.
20. **Include agroforestry in the second work programme (2026-2030) of the National Climate Adaptation Plan (PNACC-2).** PNACC-2 was approved in 2020, and will be refreshed in the 2026-2030 work-programme, currently under development. Hopefully this will contain clear and ambitious targets for the establishment and maintenance of agroforestry. For example, the Spanish Registry of Carbon Footprint, Offsetting, and CO2 Absorption Projects should be amended to include agroforestry systems on agricultural land and/or land with low tree density.

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- The SCALARE project (PRIMA - 2025-2028) <https://www.scalare-project.eu/>
- The AGROFORESTEAM project (PRIMA/PCI2025-163235- 2025-2027) <https://www.agroforesteam.org/>
- The LIFE MIDMACC project (LIFE18 CCA/ES/001099) <https://life-midmacc.eu/>

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